

BB-2208 | HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Sotorindu Restaurant and Catering/Katimahar Agri Park

Registration number: 19B0168

ABSTRACT

Sotorindu Restaurant and Catering is a well-known food chain in Brunei and famed for its iconic Soto. It is owned by a motivated, self-driven owner named, Haji Zainal Bin Haji Safar. His first branch was opened in 2001 and then expanded to six other locations throughout the Brunei-Muara district. Other than the restaurant, he also invested in a farm in Kampung Masin and started-up a 100-acre natural park, Katimahar Agri Park.

Throughout his journey in this food and beverage industry, it would be normal for Haji Zainal to encounter challenges not only in managing the business but also in sustaining his employees' performance. In any industry, employees play a huge role in keeping the company operating smoothly. However, it is not easy for every employer to maintain their employees' motivation, dedication, and commitment to the company.

Hence, this essay will elaborate on the human resource aspects such as the issues, recommendations as well as the solutions that have been made based on the article of a local brand in the food and beverage industry, Soto Rindu Restaurant and Catering.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In spite of the recognition and success, the Sotorindu restaurant has its own issues and challenges. As seen in the article, Soto Rindu could be implementing the Digital model of human resource management due to the mention of their employees could be feeling a bit demotivated which could lead to a couple of concerns that have been mentioned in the article.

For instance, as seen in the article, Haji Zainal was expecting preferable governmental support, specifically in terms of morale and financial aid throughout his profession including better infrastructure such as roads, water supply, and electricity for the availability and comfort of people who are visiting or staying at the Katimahar Agri Park as well as the employees who are working there every day.

As employees are one of the vital assets in any business industry, it is important that their needs have to be fulfilled in order to make them productive or feeling motivated throughout their working period. In this case, the sounds of the infrastructure stated, in particular, the road as an

example would make the employees feel demotivated as the road to their work might be in a condition where it would damage their vehicle or even threaten their safety. This would lead to the employees to feel unproductive to their work and would not give their best effort on the tasks. This can be supported by looking at Maslow's hierarchy of needs as well where Maslow emphasized the idea that individuals are more motivated when they feel that the company or organization is able to fulfill their basic needs up to the highest level of self-satisfactory needs.

Furthermore, Haji Zainal can be said to be a fastidious and conscientious person where he would always ensure that everything is being done ethically and not violating any laws, especially in ensuring that the foods served are clean and the 'halal' is not doubted. Hence, it is said that Soto Rindu kitchen and the employees are regularly inspected in response to the personality trait mentioned.

Though this might pressure the employees and bring tension to the workplace as it could lead him to remark even the smallest mistake or error such as the wrong taste of dish could be asked to be thrown away even when the mistake is just fried and non-fried, for example. However, Haji Zainal could not be able to tolerate it as it could affect the company greatly without the employees realizing it. As a result, this could demotivate employees should there is a lack of understanding between them. However, despite how strict and meticulous Haji Zainal is, he would not ignore his employees' welfare in assuring that they are satisfied in working with him and for Soto Rindu as a company.

On top of that, everyday for over two years as mentioned, Haji Zainal is said to be experiencing quite numerous cases of theft from his offices and the stolen amount was not little, in fact, it was hundreds of dollars. This act might be done by the employees or might as well be from outsiders. If it is really by the staff, Haji Zainal needs to find out who and ask why they did it. For instance, hundreds of dollars are not a small amount and there would be a reason why they committed such an act. They might need extras on their finances or they might be struggling with something.

Lastly, he also brings up that the competitions with the other Malay agripreneurs are stiff and there would be a longstanding phenomenon within the community which he makes reference to

as *Melayu makan Melayu*. He mentioned that Malays are vulnerable to jealousy and lack of support for fellow Malays who are well-known without being spiteful.

CASE ANALYSIS

Digital HRM is also known under different terms such as e-hrm, virtual HR(M), HR intranet, web-based HR, computer-based human resource management systems (CHRIS), and HR portals (Huub Ruël, Tanya Bondarouk, Jan Kees Looise, 2004). Digital HRM is the usage or the application of IT in HR practices as well the functions, covering all the areas of HR, such as hiring, recognitions, performance management, providing benefits, deciding compensations, learning and developing, payroll as well as rewards through the use of social, mobile, analytics and cloud (SMAC) (Verlinden, n.d).

According to AIHR Digital, the implementation of IT for HR functions or practices could improve the engagement between employers and employees, to boost employees experience as well as to reduce time in doing tasks that are repetitive. Lepak and Shell (1998) determined that there are three types of HRM that organizations can choose from to 'offer' HR services either by face-to-face or via electronic namely, operational HRM, relational HRM, and transformational HRM.

A bit of elaboration about the three HRM starting with the first area is operational HRM that has to do with administrative functions such as payroll and personnel data administration. Moving on to relational HRM that is far from the administrative, however, it is an HR tool that supports basic company processes, for example, the recruitment and selection of new employees, providing as well as conducting training, performance and assessment management, and rewards. Transformational HRM is the third area that has similar functions as operational HRM and essentially, this type or area of HRM is handling the regular everyday administrative activities that include the administration of benefits, review, and publication of workplace policies, and investigation of workplace problems.

In the case of Sotorindu, digital models of HRM can be applied to encounter the challenges or issues that Haji Zainal may have faced or currently facing. For instance, the issue of theft could be solved by implementing an electronic pos system where the cashier or where the company

stores their daily transaction are kept in a computerized system where only authorized people can access it. By implementing this method, it could reduce the theft issue Soto Rindu was facing as all transactions will be recorded online, hence if there is some un-tally figure, it could be detected immediately. In addition, these internal controls are essential in order to avoid mishandling of money and to protect the assets in case of loss or theft.

TYPES

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- **Operational**- Administrative functions. (eg- payroll and employee personal data.)
- **Relational** - Supporting business processes by means of training, recruitment, performance management etc.
- **Transformational**- Strategic HR activities such as knowledge management, strategic re-orientation.

“An organisation may choose to pursue E-HRM policies from any number of these tiers to achieve their HR goals.”

System approach to HRM

Other than that, installing a security system such as displaying CCTV systems both internal and external of the premises in order to keep the criminal away or to find out who is the culprit if there is any case of theft happening again in the future. Furthermore, installing the CCTV system could give the employees as well as the visitors a sense of safety and peace whenever they are in the establishment and to include that it is part of the employees' welfare to provide them the comfort and safety in their workplace.

Moreover, a virtual reality (VR) training could be executed to solve the wastage issue as Haji Zainal is famed for being precise and observing every detail which could pressure the employees. For instance, by implementing this technology into the business, it could enhance the effectiveness of the training, cut down the waste cost as well as an increase high-performing

employees and employee retention (Fell, 2018). As Sotorindu has expanded to six other locations, it is necessary for keeping the taste of the dish consistent in all of the six branches. Therefore, it is crucial for the employees to learn the proper information or in this case, the correct measurements of the ingredients in order to represent the company brand, Sotorindu. There are numbers of benefits that can be gained by utilizing an interactive virtual reality to meet all the training needs, for instance, if an experience is developed, within this experience, workers can learn and retrain without any additional expense and the restaurant is capable to obtain pieces of information on how the employees work or perform, to see who are good on the job and who need more training.

Due to Haji Zainal being a particular man, he could prefer his employees to work by hand, for instance, chopping bags of onions by hand, but changing to modern technologies could be more beneficial for the business. For Instance, the business could provide an electronic or any machine that could help them to produce sliced or minced onions in a more efficient way within a less amount of time compared to chop them by hand which the employees would drain their productivity level eventually after repeating the same task every day.

PROS AND CONS

Looking at the solutions given, there would be clearly a few pros and cons that come along with it. For instance, by implementing the VR training, the restaurant is able to establish consistent training that can be repeated to ensure that talking points are addressed, eliminating the possibility for manager error. Hence, it could boost up the employees' performance and they would work to their full potential with the help of technology-induced training. As a result, Sotorindu could gain more competitive advantage.

On top of that, implementing this approach to Sotorindu could also improve both employee retention and welfare as well, as for example, installing a CCTV system would give the employees peace of mind which would provide a safe environment for them to work in. Moreover, providing the tools or machines that could help them to maximize their efficiency in working could improve their welfare, as a result, an increase in employee retention.

Another advantage that the solutions provided are that it is saving enhancing the efficiency of the workforce. Mentioning the VR induced training, it could help the business to diminish the needs of (paid) training managers to attend most training sessions. Apart from that, restaurant training by using VR may save or lower the cost as it could prevent any potential injuries either if they are working in the kitchen, warehouse or the tools and appliances could be damaged or wasting the resources such as the ingredients during training.

Despite the benefits, these solutions would have a high cost in expenses. Additionally, this digital model is offering high upfront cost solutions, for instance, the VR training programs, as well as the installation of the security system including the types of machinery, would not come cheap. Furthermore, these things would require either a software and hardware update every period of time in order for them to fully function to the maximum potential.

The pros and cons that can be extracted from the solution suggested above are as follows.

PROS	CONS
It increases employee's performance as it promotes the highest level of motivation for the employees.	The cost of the expenses would be high due to the prices.
It improves employee retention due to innovation in the training.	Every period of time, the software would need updates to function to the fullest.
It upgrades employee welfare as it offers the employee convenience in the workplace.	
It could increase the efficiency of the employees in doing their duties.	

Table of the pros and cons

CONCLUSION

To conclude from this article analysis, entrepreneurs could never run from challenges and issues within companies. However, despite having the challenges, there will always be solutions and Sotorindu is one of the companies that managed to prove this statement. Even after years of being in the industry, Sotorindu and Haji Zainal himself did not give up and kept striving to improve the company.

Apart from the human resource aspects, some recommendations can be presented for Sotorindu such as on-the-job training to ensure that they are doing their duties according to Sotorindu's standard. As Haji Zainal is meticulous, this way of training could help to solve the issue as the employees would be more skillful as well as well-trained in the kitchen, thus their abilities and capabilities can be developed to gain a competitive advantage. As Haji Zainal has requested for better water supply, he should be taking into account the cost that may incur which might affect the employees' wages and income of the company should the water supply be used otherwise.

Last but not least this concluded that despite how big or small an organization or company is, what matters the most in the entrepreneurial world is how we manage to act upon the challenges and keep striving, learning as well as trying new risks.

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